

The Political Sociology of Cultural Schism in Türkiye

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Abstract

This study examines the historical, epistemological and political bases of cultural divergence in Türkiye within the framework of modernization literature. The fundamental argument of this article is the reason why cultural polarization in Türkiye stems not only from periodic political rivalries. Rather, it is directed through long-term epistemological and normative tensions produced by late modernization experiences. The study asserts that modernization is not producing homogeneous social integration in non-Western societies. Instead, it has created persistent conflicts between different lifestyles, identity regimes, and understandings of truth. The example of Türkiye proposes an important example in comparative political science literature. This example is demonstrating how historical tensions between secular-modern knowledge systems and traditional religious affiliations reproduce cultural polarization. This article evaluates modernization theory, political sociology, identity and cultural schizophrenia all together. Methodologically, the study combines comparative historical analysis and an interpretive political sociology approach. In terms of empirical data, current research data were used, published by KONDA, Istanbul Economy Research and Friedrich Naumann Foundation. The findings show that the cultural schism in Türkiye is deepening along spatial, generational, and digital dimensions. Furthermore, digital media spaces are strengthening cultural clusters, thereby narrowing areas of social contact. This study contributes to the literature on modernization and polarization in Türkiye by conceptualizing cultural polarization as a form of epistemological conflict beyond ideological differentiation.

Keywords: Cultural Polarization, Modernization, Epistemological Conflict, Political Sociology, Türkiye

Introduction

Modernization has long been evaluated in social sciences literature in terms of progression, rationalization and political institutionalization (Weber, 1978: 24-56; Parsons, 1971: 12-29). Classical modernization theories largely treated modernity as a universal model of development centered on the Western European experience; economic development, secularization, and bureaucratic centralization were regarded as the core dynamics of this transformation. (Rostow, 1960: 4-16; Parsons, 1971:12-29). However, modernization experiences of non-Western societies show that modernity not only produces just economic and institutional transformation; but also creates lasting tensions between cultural belongings, lifestyles and understanding of truth at the same time (Eisenstadt, 2000: 1-29). Especially, modernization in late modernized

societies has produced conflicting relationships between different identity regimes, rather than a homogenous social integration (Shayegan, 1991: 63-86).

Therefore, cultural polarization is not a phenomenon that can be explained solely through choice behavior or ideological differentiations. Current political sociology literature shows that polarization is deepening through lifestyle, cultural belonging and daily life practices (Connolly, 1995: 93-119; Göle, 2011:31-32). With this, a significant portion of current studies examine polarization within the framework of populism, center-periphery relation, political competition or identity politics (Mardin, 1973: 169-190). The relation between cultural polarization and the long-lasting normative tensions created by modernization has been addressed in a relatively limited way.

From this point of view, the example of Türkiye introduces a remarkable modernization experience. With the transition process from Ottoman Empire to Republic of Türkiye, modernization has been shaped not only as a new model of the state, but also as a project to build a new society and identity (Zürcher, 2004: 181-210). The modernization of the Republic regarded secularization, centralization and rationalization as the fundamental references of the society (Ahmad, 1993: 56-89). However, this period has generated long-lasting tensions among traditional social structures and secular-modern government ideology (Heper, 1985: 45-78). Particularly, after 1980, with neoliberal transformation, urbanization, digitalization and the rise of political Islam have made these tensions more visible. Thus, cultural schism became the central dynamics of social life (Keyder, 2003:33-61; Göle, 2011: 87-112).

This study examines the cultural division in Türkiye based on its historical and political foundations. The fundamental argument of this article is that periodic political crises are not the reason for cultural polarization in Türkiye. This situation is shaped more by the long-lasting normative tensions produced by the experience of late modernization. The study focuses on three fundamental questions:

- How does modernization generate cultural tensions in late-modernizing societies?
- How has Türkiye's modernization experience shaped the political formation of cultural identities?
- What social consequences follow from the spatial, digital, and generational manifestations of cultural cleavage?

This study offers three fundamental contributions to the literature. First of all, the study conceptualizes cultural polarization in Türkiye as a form of cultural and epistemological conflict rather than ideological differentiation. Secondly, it associates modernization theory and political sociology literature through a cultural schizophrenia approach (Shayegan, 1991:63-86). Lastly, it shows how digitalization, spatial segregation and cultural differentiation deepen cultural schism (Sunstein, 2001: 9-25).

The article explains methodological framework, and then discusses modernization, cultural polarization and cultural schizophrenia literature. The final section analyzes the historical and current appearances of cultural schism in Türkiye.

Methodological Framework

This study adopts an interpretive political sociology approach. Cultural polarization is treated not as a temporary political division reducible to voting behavior, but as a structural social phenomenon historically shaped within processes of modernization (Göle,2011: 31-32). In this

regard, the study examines cultural schism within the frameworks of historical and political contexts.

In this study, we used a secondary data analysis method. The theoretical framework draws on the literatures on modernization, political sociology, identity, cultural polarization, and cultural schizophrenia. The study combines comparative historical analysis with an interpretive analytical approach. Within this scope, studies of Eisenstadt (2000), Connolly (1995), Göle (2011), Shayegan (1991), Mardin (1973), Mağcupyan (1998) and Esposito (2003) are taken as the fundamental reference sources.

For the empirical phase, current researches published by KONDA, İstanbul Economic Research (İEA) and Friedrich Naumann Foundation (FNF) have been utilized. These data are used for examining spatial, generational and digital appearances of cultural polarization (İEA& FNF, 2024:14-28).

This study uses comparative historical analysis and interpreter analysis approaches together. In the historical dimension, transitions of cultural identities and social segregations are examined in the process extending from Ottoman modernization to present-day Türkiye (Zürcher, 2004: 181-210). In terms of analytical dimension, the study evaluates how permanent tensions have produced between secular-modern lifestyles of modernization and traditional belongings (Shayegan, 1991:63-86).

Within this framework, cultural polarization is examined as a multi-layer social process shaped through lifestyle, social belonging, daily life practices and digital public spaces (Sunstein, 2001: 9-25; Connolly, 1995: 93-119).

The Relationship between Modernization and Identity

Modernization in non-Western societies not only caused institutional transformations. Moreover, that produced historical ruptures in which collective belongings, cultural identities and understanding of truths have been reconsidered. Modernity in late-modernized societies has been associated with rationalization and centralization. However, modernity in traditional societies is mostly experienced with cultural disintegration and decrement of belongings. Accordingly, modernization states ongoing tensions between conceptions of different civilizations and information systems. The conflicts between Secular-modern references and traditional belongings generate more different lifestyles than homogeneous social integrations.

The founding discourse of modernism is to create social order in a rational, hierarchical, and collective structure. Modernity has produced a frame that has made sense of daily life through order, control and classification practices (Çiğdem, 2004:83). At this process, individuals and societies have been identified through dichotomous categories like me-other, inside-outside, and local-foreign. On the other hand, modern transformation not only paved the way for new institutions, but also new cultural boundaries (Gelekçi, 2011:76-97).

Modernism, when viewed from a sociological perspective, expresses the transition from the form of traditional society to modern society (Tuna, 2011:5-6). Nevertheless, this transition is not only an institutional reconstruction. The modern project has weakened the determining influence of religious references. Moreover, this also produced a secular rupture that historical

understanding of individual-centered gain strength (Kahraman, 2001:13-14). As a result of this, the source of political and social legitimacy has shifted through secular rationality.

This transition has made clearer the question of how collective belongings have been established and political identification is shaped. Identity is one of the fundamental belonging mechanisms that how individuals and collective actors describe themselves (Pratt and Foreman, 2000: 18-42). From this perspective, identity has a central function of collective belongings and political borders (Marshall, 1999: 407-408). According to Bilgin, identity is one of the fundamental means producing mechanisms that an individual differs from others (Bilgin, 1997: 199-200).

With modern transition, formation of identities has been influenced directly from changes of historical and social changes. Identities are built from the relational conflict with the “other”, while individuals and collectives describe themselves through differences (Bostancı, 1998: 52). In this respect, identity is not the one that only produces belonging, but at the same time functions as a political mechanism that draws cultural boundaries. Modernization processes led to identities taking more visible political forms. Besides, individuals have begun to describe themselves not only with cultural belongings but also through ideologic and value-based conflicts. According to Connolly (1995: 93), in order to protect their persistence, identities reproduce diversity from otherness. For this reason, identity scope can be discriminatory rather than inclusive.

For Mahçupyan (1998:46), the process of forming identity is related with individuals or society and the groups that should not resemble themselves. In the situations where cultural distance is feeling threatened, identities could be shaped more rigid and defensive, and turned into political and socio-psychologic safety instruments. Especially, modernization in late-modernized societies is not only a historical transition, but also means establishment of new identity regimes. Thereby, modernization has moved to the center of political rivalry from cultural identities that caused new identity struggles beyond institutional changes.

Modernizm, Islamism and Epistemological Tension

When identities are evaluated based on the ways of understanding life, it can be seen that traditional/Islamic thought and modern thoughts are distinctly in conflict. From an Islamic point of view, the ultimate source of knowledge is the divine will and the measure of the truth based on the divine mind (Kaya, 2006:200). Conversely, modern thoughts are based on secularization of knowledge, and place debate, inquiry and critical thinking in the center of daily life. For this reason, the tension between modernism and traditional religious thoughts is not only about cultural differences. This also expresses a historical field where different understandings of truth are in conflict (Salguni, 2005:17).

The intellectual foundation of Traditional/Islamic approach is revelation. Islamic Thought produces a holistic frame to make sense of daily life through concepts like God, after life, good-bad and truth. The Prophet’s practices, legal schools, madrasas, catechetical traditions, the ulema, and religious authorities have become the institutional carriers of this structure (Yıldırım, 1995:117). In this framework, knowledge has been evaluated not only as a product of individual intellect, but also a part of legitimized order of transcendent values.

According to Nilüfer (2011: 31-32), the fundamental battlefield of traditional/Islamic movements are habitus, cultural codes and lifestyles. On the other hand, the tension between modernity and tradition lives on not only through ideological differences. This is also a power struggle fed from daily practices, forms of institutional visibility and fields of subjectivity. Including areas, such as headscarf, family structure, consumption habits and education practices are transformed into symbolic battlefields in which secular lifestyle and religious belongings confront each other. For this reason, lifestyle discussions are producing political conflict areas connected with public legitimacy and power relations, beyond cultural differences.

Together with the secularization process, scientific knowledge has begun to take the place of value systems where religious systems are decisive. Then, the source of legitimacy has begun to shift from religious authorities to modern thought systems (Yıldırım, 1995:129). Especially, this transition in late modernized societies is not only an institutional change. This also means a reconstruction of collective memory, cultural belongings and identities. Most of the time, modernization experiences have carried the fear of cultural dissolution and identity lost in Islamic societies.

As Esposito stated (2003: 102-103), modern transition produced a clear separation between the Westernized elite minority and the social majority that traditional Islamic governed in most of the Islamic societies. This differentiation not only stayed in daily practices, but also created structural inequalities in the areas of power, privilege, knowledge production and public representation. Westernized elites evaluate modernization as the compulsory condition of progress. However, this evaluation has strengthened the cultural exclusion and crisis of representation in traditional places. In this respect, cultural schism can be evaluated as the current social appearance of historical tension between traditional belongings and modern thought systems.

Modernity experience in non-Westernized societies has caused the existence of different intellectual universes in the same historical moments at the same time. While secular institutions, scientific minds and modern lifestyles increased their effect, traditional belongings, religious references and historical memory continued their public effects. This situation shows that modernization processes do not only produce institutional transition, but also create segmented and tense structures in individuals' world of meaning. In late modernized societies, intertwining of different civilization concepts in the same social area caused producing contradictory and hybrid forms in relation between modernity and tradition. Daryush Shayegan's conceptualization of "cultural schizophrenia" offers an important theoretical perspective for explaining segmented modernity experience.

Cultural Schizophrenia in Traditional Societies

The concept of 'cultural schizophrenia,' developed by Daryush Shayegan, seeks to explain the epistemological and cultural cleavage that emerges in traditional societies encountering modernity. According to Shayegan, societies that resist modernity at the civilizational level attempt, on the one hand, to function within the material and institutional realities of the secular-modern world while, on the other, continuing to interpret that world through inherited habitus and maps of meaning. This situation is causing the emergence of fragmented, contradictory and discontinuous forms of consciousness, especially in non-Westernized societies. The

simultaneous rejection and internalization of modernity at the level of daily life is producing a hybrid social structure. This situation is forcing individuals to take positions in different epistemological universes.

Shayegan's approach (1991: 63-86) states that the tension between modernism and traditional epistemology produces not only cultural, but also psychologic, political and social results. On the other hand, different epistemological systems exist simultaneously at the same social area in the modernization process. As a result, that causes individuals and communities to form fragmented forms of consciousness while they attempt to make sense of the world. Modern-secular life practices and traditional religious belongings reproduced conflictingly in the same social structure (Göle, 2011: 31-32). Cultural schism is feeding not only from ideological differences, but also from different truth regimes that simultaneously exist in a structural tension area.

According to Shayegan (1991:63), civilizations which are based on different paradigms make an impact on the same social sphere simultaneously. This situation causes deformation and fragmentation in individuals' intellectual worlds. In addition, this also leads to the creation of hybrid forms of consciousness because of the articulation of unrelated epistemological and cultural elements within the same structure. Shayegan defines this process as "the clash between ideas that have no connection with phenomena and social realities". Modernization exposes a fragile consciousness structure where different knowledge systems are articulated in contradiction, rather than producing a holistic transformation.

According to him, this patching practice is either an articulation of modern discourse through traditional content, or a placement of traditional discourse through modern content (Shayegan, 1991:86). While Westernization appears in the first, Islamization appears in the second. However, the resulting structure in both situations produces fragile and twisted hybridity, more than a consistent synthesis. Cultural schizophrenia is not limited to superficial agreements between modernism and traditionalism. On the contrary, this situation is related to necessary coexistence of epistemological elements that do not belong to each other within the same social structure.

Over time, this hybrid structure creates a conscious structure which can be described as "double illusion" at the social level. According to Shayegan (2013:46-47) while Western values are criticized, Western lifestyle, technology and cultural codes are internalized at the same time. While conservative discourse is trying to protect current cultural structure, it is articulated in the modernization process at the level of daily practices. This situation shows that the ideological resistance towards modernization was unable to prevent reproducing modern lifestyles on a practical level. The conflict between modernization and tradition not only reproduces through political discourses. This conflict is also reproduced by daily life practices, consumption habits and cultural behaviors.

In this context, cultural schizophrenia can not only be evaluated only as an individual psychological situation. This is also a structural crisis area that produces social and political results. In societies that are under the pressure of modernization, individuals are forced to live in different epistemological universes simultaneously (Shayegan, 1991:63-86). While daily practices, consumption habits and institutional belongings of secular-modern life exist, traditional values, religious affiliations and historical memory persist (Göle, 2011: 31-32). This situation leads to cultural tensions becoming tougher, especially during the political

mobilization process. In modernizing Eastern societies where, political Islam has broadened its base, the potential of cultural schism is becoming more visible. This situation is also related to societies that have contradictory structures of consciousness (Esposito, 2003: 102-103). This schism not only expresses ideological differences; but also embodies two distinct moral frameworks, value systems, mentalities and daily practices.

Cultural schizophrenia approach states that modernization in non-Westernized societies does not produce a linear and holistic transition. On the contrary, this causes fragile structures that have different historical memories, ways of thinking and life styles intertwined. This situation reveals that the modernization process is influential at the individual level of consciousness and forms of social organization. In addition, this process creates long-term effects on forms of political affiliations. Especially in late modernization experiences that state-society relations are redefined, cultural schism can acquire a political and institutional character in time. The modernization experience of Türkiye is an important example for examining how historical fractures in question shape cultural schism.

The Historical Construction of the Cultural Schism in Türkiye

In order to understand the historical origins of cultural schism in Türkiye the transition extending from Ottoman modernization to the Republican era should be evaluated holistically. The military and economic decline of the Ottoman Empire against the West led state elites to quest for reform (Lewis, 2002:21-58; Berkes, 2002: 25-74). During this process, the West is not only referred to as a representative model for technical superiority, but also a new civilization paradigm (Mardin, 1991: 9-18; Çiğdem, 2002: 61-69). Modernization arguments, beyond technical reforms, produced an epistemological and politic argument area for in which civilization axis Ottoman society will be repositioned.

Modernization attempts, starting with Tanzimat Reforms, aimed to strengthen the central structure of the state and adapt the Western institutions to Ottoman social structure (Berkes, 2002: 137-182). However, this transition process produced evident conflicts between traditional social structure and understanding of the modern state.

On the one side, reformist elites have taken the place that sees the West as the fundamental model for progress and liberation. On the other side, there were traditional segments who believed this transition was eroding the historical memory and religious references (Lewis, 2002:111-165; Mardin 1991: 11-34). Modernization of Ottoman produced long-term cultural tension between lifestyles and value systems besides institutional transitions.

Together with II. Constitutional Era, modernization discussions have produced more visible ideological clustering. Ideologies like Westernism, Turkish Nationalism and Islamism generate different answers for how Ottoman can be saved. After that, modernization discussions have turned into identity discussions (Mardin, 2008: 45-67). Particularly, according to the approach developed by Ziya Gökalp states that technical aspects of the West can be taken, but national culture must be protected (Gökalp, 1976: 15-28). This approach has become one the most important theoretical references of conservative-modernist synthesis search in Türkiye (Göle, 2011:31-32). Modernization discussions in the late-Ottoman era produced not only political reform searches. This also caused ideological struggles of how the relation between modernity and tradition will be established.

Together with the establishment of the Republic of Türkiye, the modernization process has acquired more radical and central character. Republic elitists aimed to construct a national identity by establishing a strong distance from the Ottoman past (Berkes, 2002:524-530; Zürcher, 2004: 181-190). Secularism, modern education system, secular law and Western lifestyle have been determined as the fundamental normative framework of the Republic (Lewis, 2002: 280-295). This form of modernization has no longer meant only administrative reforms, but also reconstruction of everyday life, cultural affiliations and public appearance. However, this form of modernization has not been equally accepted by different segments of society (Mardin, 1973: 169-190). Republic modernization has been moved to a different dimension in rural strata and social structures that have strong religious references. Most of the time, this modernization has been perceived as a form of cultural alienation.

Modernization in Türkiye has not only been a process of rationalization and progress. This process has also produced a cultural tension area that is deepening between the center and periphery. Şerif Mardin's center-periphery framework presents an important theoretical framework in order to explain this decomposition. According to Mardin (1973:173) while Republican elitists represented the center, traditional-religious segments of society forming the periphery had been excluded from this representation area for a long time. As a result, cultural schism has become a historical area of confictions where not only ideological differences, but also struggles for political representations, cultural visibility and social legitimacy are decisive.

Together with the transition to a multi-party system after 1950, the visibility of peripheral social segments started to increase. Democratic Party era can be evaluated as one of the major turning points in which traditional-conservative social segments were more strongly included in the political system (Mardin, 1973: 170-181). This process has prepared the ground for historical tension between central and periphery to become visible through political representations (Zürcher, 2004: 221-250; Ahmad, 1993: 102-135). Cultural schism has begun to be reproduced not only through cultural affiliations, but also through political power and representation struggles.

Neoliberal transition after 1980 caused cultural schism to take new forms in Türkiye. While the processes of urbanization, media spread, consumption culture and globalization reshape everyday life, the economic and cultural visibility of conservative segments has also increased (Keyder, 2003: 33-61). Especially, the rise of Anatolian capital, the formation of the formation of conservative middle classes and the expansion of new media have strengthened the social basis of cultural polarization (Buğra & Savaşkan, 2014: 52-88; Göle, 2011: 87-112). In this way, cultural schism has ceased to be a state-centered ideological decomposition. After that, it has transformed into a multilayered social division through consumption practices, social places and everyday lifestyles.

With the rise of the Welfare Party in the 1990s, and then the rise of the AK Party's coming to power, the cultural schism in Türkiye transformed into a new hegemony struggle (Toprak, 2005: 167-186; Özbudun, 2006: 543-557). In this period, secular-modern segments thought that founding values of the Republic were eroded. However, conservative social segments defend that they acquire visibility in public spaces from which they were excluded for many years (Göle, 2011: 87-112). Lifestyle, religious visibility and cultural affiliations have become one of the fundamental axes of political rivalry. Cultural schism in Türkiye is not a phenomenon that can only be explained by ideological differences. This schism takes form through historical

memory, lifestyle, class transformation, spatial segregation and epistemological reference systems. The process in question also produces a multilayered social conflict area.

Cultural schism in Türkiye has historically not been limited to disagreements of state elites and traditional segments of society. In time, this caused different forms of affiliations to be repositioned in social life. Especially economic transformations, urbanization dynamics and widespread communication areas have made more visible the distance of different identity clusters. Thus, cultural differentiations have ceased to be temporary tensions which are special for specific historical eras. In addition, this has transformed into more permanent decomposition, affecting daily relations, public interactions and social affiliations. This situation makes it necessary to examine how cultural schism in Türkiye deepens on a social level.

The Deepening of Cultural Cleavage in Türkiye: Social Fragmentation

Social segregation in Türkiye can be evaluated as one of the more visible forms of intellectual, political and social tensions that historically produced by the modernization process (Shayegan, 1991: 63-86). Research conducted in recent years shows that the segregation in Türkiye is not only because of differences of political choices. This also shows that it has transformed into a structural segregation through lifestyles, moral value systems, religious affiliations and daily everyday practices (Göle, 2011: 87-112; KONDA, 2022: 12-27). Current research conducted by IEA and Friedrich Naumann Foundation also prove that generational, special and identity-based clustering are becoming more prominent (IEA & FNF, 2024: 14-28). This situation shows segregation not only limited to political areas, but also transformed into permanent boundaries of affiliations in different areas of everyday life.

The research prepared by Istanbul Economy Research (IEA) and Friedrich Naumann Foundation states how polarization in Türkiye reproduced at the spatial, generational and ideological level (IEA & FNF, 2024). According to the results, polarization continuously increased, especially since the 2002 period; and after 2011, this has become more visible and severe. The transformation of political segregation into cultural affiliations in time has caused the reproduction of “us” and “other” distinctions in everyday life. Especially, the approximately 22% jump that occurred during June 7- November 1 2015 demonstrates that this has intensified the existing fault lines of current political crises. After 2020, the polarization has not been limited to specific political clusters. On the contrary, it transformed into a structural phenomenon among the country.

Table 1. Temporal Deepening of Cultural Polarization in Türkiye

Period	Empirical Finding	Analytical Implication
Post-2002	Rising polarization trends	Cultural identities increasingly shape political alignments
Post-2011	Intensified visibility of polarization	Consolidation of “us vs. them” social boundaries
June–Nov 2015	Sharp escalation in polarization	Political crises deepen cultural fault lines
Post-2020	Nationwide diffusion of polarization	Polarization becomes structurally embedded

These findings suggest that polarization in Türkiye increasingly operates through durable identity boundaries extending beyond electoral competition.

The polarization, which becomes more visible through quantitative data, can emerge in symbolic and confliction forms at specific historical turning points. The Gezi Park protests demonstrate that social division in Türkiye operates not only through political competition but also through conflicts over lifestyle, public space, and regimes of visibility. According to Özen and Avcı (2013: 35), the Gezi Park protests represent a historical turning point that the tension between secular-modern lifestyle and conservative social imagination becomes more visible. In this process, the arguments about how public spaces will be defined, boundaries of individual freedom, and the legitimacy of visibility made more visible the symbolic dimension of segregation in Türkiye. In other words, polarization is not only a political rivalry related with choice behavior, it also appears as the form of struggle between how daily life can be and opposite imaginations.

Similarly, KONDA's research shows that the distance between different social segments in Türkiye is deepening especially through lifestyle, religion, sects and political affiliations (KONDA,2022). The willingness to marry, live next to, or form close relationships. With the reduction of connection, prejudices and insecurities have mutually become permanent. Thence, identity-based decompositions reproduced not only through ideological differences, but also through the distance relations which forms everyday practices. This lack of communication has become visible not just among relations of individuals, but also spatial arrangement patterns.

One of the important dimensions of decomposition is spatial clustering that emerges at the geographical level. IEA research shows that individuals who have similar political cultural affiliations started to have begun to concentrate in the same regions. Especially, while secular lifestyle is evidential in the coastal areas; conservative and religious identity clusters are evidential in the Central Anatolia and Eastern Anatolia Regions (IEA & FNF, 2024: 14-16). The decomposition that occurs at the level of neighborhood in metropolitans causes to reduce connection among different segments in daily life, and similar affiliation segments are producing more closed social areas. After 2020, the significant rise of polarization level coastal areas shows that this decomposition is not limited to certain regions anymore. On the contrary, this has become a national phenomenon.

Table 2. Spatial Manifestations of Cultural Polarization

Spatial Dimension	Empirical Finding	Sociological Interpretation
Coastal regions	Higher concentration of secular lifestyles	Cultural clustering intensifies
Central & Eastern Anatolia	Stronger conservative-religious identities	Traditional social spaces consolidate
Metropolitan cities	Neighborhood-level segregation emerges	Decline in intergroup social contact
Post-2020	Polarization spreads nationwide	Cultural division becomes geographically normalized

According to Putnam's social capital approach, the reduction of connection between different groups has affected social integrations by weakening the trust relations (Putnam, 200: 22-24). In Türkiye, the clusters which become visible at the level of neighborhoods, cities and regions are also leading to fragmentation of the social capital. The narrowing of shared public spaces and concentration of similar affiliation groups in their own peripheries reduces mutual dialog opportunities and produces more permanent relations. This transition becomes more visible especially for affiliations and lifestyles of young generations.

One of the remarkable findings of the research is that polarization is reproducing among young generations through lifestyles and value systems. The differentiation among young people is formed by more religious affiliations, gender, individual freedoms and visibility areas, rather than classic right-left axis (IEA & FNF, 2024: 24-28). Especially in the subjects of women's rights, LGBTQ+ issues, understanding of individual freedom and public visibility, normative differences emerge. This situation shows that the tension between modernity and tradition continues among new generations. Thus, current polarization is not only a historical ideological conflict, but also a form of differentiation that reproduced as generational. One of the fundamental areas of this generational differentiation is digital communication platforms.

Table 3. Cultural Polarization Among Younger Generations

Dimension	Empirical Observation	Analytical Interpretation
Lifestyle preferences	Central axis of differentiation	Identity conflict becomes normalized
Religious belonging	Secular-conservative divide persists	Generational cultural cleavage continues
Gender issues	Strong divergence on women's rights & LGBTQ+ debates	Competing moral frameworks intensify
Freedom perceptions	Deepening normative disagreements	Modernity-tradition tension persists
Digital media	Expansion of echo chambers	Polarization reproduced online

According to Sunstein (2001: 9-25), digital media platforms produce an "echo chamber" effect because these platforms cause individuals to encounter only contents that reinforce their own perspectives. Social media platforms in Türkiye transform into echo chambers, since similar affiliation clusters reproduce their own thoughts, rather than being a public space that encounters different opinions (KONDA, 2022: 12-27). Especially, the usage of digital media among young generations clustering according to political and cultural affiliations leads to reduced connection and deepens the prejudices between different segments (IEA&FNF, 2023: 14-28). Digital public space is becoming a new social space that reproduces identity-based polarizations, rather than serving as a communication platform that strengthens democratic pluralism (Tüfekçi, 2017: 105-132).

This social vision that cultural schism has reached shows that polarization is a deep and multilayered structure that cannot be explained only by periodic political tensions. Extending as far as from lifestyles and spatial clusters, to generational differentiations and digital communication areas, these forms of fragmentations point out that the public base is getting

narrower. In particular, the reduction of communication among different social segments strengthens the affiliation-based boundaries by limiting the mutual understandings and negotiation opportunities. For this reason, cultural schism in Türkiye is not just a result of political polarization. In addition, this can also be evaluated as a formation of historical tensions that institutionalized in contemporary social relations during the modernization process. In this framework, the study holistically evaluates the cultural schism through the historical origins, intellectual background and current social reflections.

Conclusion

This study has asserted that cultural schism is not merely a form of polarization arising from episodic political competition. Rather, it is also forming through long-term epistemological and historical tensions produced by late modernization experiences. Throughout the study, modernization is not evaluated only as an economic development or institutional transition process. Instead, modernization has been considered as a historical breaking point that reconstructs truth regimes, collective affiliations and daily life practices. Within this framework, the example of Türkiye shows that modernization does not produce a homogenous social integration in non-Western societies. On the contrary, modernization in these societies creates fragmented social structures in which different epistemological universes coexist simultaneously in the same structure.

One of the fundamental findings of the study is that cultural schism in Türkiye does not only function through ideological differences. This schism is reproducing through lifestyle, public visibility, spatial clustering, digital communication areas and generational affiliation forms. Especially, the production of echo chambers in digital media platforms lead to reduction of communication among different social segments and deepening the mutual legitimacy crisis. This situation shows that cultural polarization is not only about the difference of political choices. Moreover, this produces a multilayered social polarization, extending as far as forms of organizations of daily life.

The cultural schizophrenia approach used in the study refers to the modernization experiment offers an important opportunity to explain why non-Westernized societies produce fragmented forms of consciousness. When this is evaluated in the framework of Shayegan's conceptualization, modern-secular lifestyles and traditional epistemological affiliations coexist simultaneously in the same social structure. This situation leads to the occurrence of hybrid but fragile identity forms. The example of Türkiye shows that these epistemological tensions are not remaining at the conscious level only, but also can produce institutional results, ranging from political mobilization processes to public space struggles.

In this context, the study conceptualizes cultural polarization as the social appearance of epistemological fragmentation that modernization produces beyond ideological rivalry. The example of Türkiye shows that social schism in late modernized societies is not only shaped from political differences. This schism is formed by the tense relations that different truth regimes, lifestyles and historical memories established within the same social structure. For this reason, cultural schism in late modernized societies should be evaluated as a problem of structural political sociology which requires rethinking the limits of democratic pluralism.

Consequently, the example of Türkiye demonstrates that cultural polarization is forming through much deeper epistemological and historical tensions rather than political rivalry in late modernized societies. For this reason, cultural schism should be evaluated not only as a manifestation of political polarization, but also as the social manifestation of the long-term epistemological fragmentation produced by modernization that modernization produces. The case of Türkiye provides an important example in comparative political science literature by demonstrating how social polarization can transform into epistemological regime conflicts.

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